

Word Cloud

When you think about mentorship, what words come to mind?

- 1) Scan QR code OR
- 2) [PollEv.com/vwelcome](https://pollev.com/vwelcome) OR
- 3) Send vwelcome to 22333

Home Again: International Engineering Student Engagement Through Peer Mentorship Program

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LAND ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

ACPA–College Student Educators International acknowledges, with respect, that the land on which our ACPA25 Convention is taking place is part of the traditional unceded homelands of the Tongva/Gabrieleño, the Acjachemen/Juaneño, and the Toongvetam peoples as well as a significant place of cultural knowledge and sacred teachings for many other tribes. This land, called Tovaangar, is home to Puvungna, “the gathering place,” the place of emergence in the origin traditions of the Tongva and Acjachemen peoples. We recognize that Puvungna is sacred land of extraordinary cultural significance that continues to serve as an active ceremonial ground today. We acknowledge that Puvungna, and the entirety of Tovaangar, remains unceded and unjustly occupied. As visitors to Tovaangar, we affirm our responsibility to listen, to learn, and to work for justice in this land.

Beyond acknowledging the land and in recognition of the impacts of historical and ongoing settler colonialism, including that perpetuated by North American institutions of higher education, ACPA actively commits to supporting professionals in higher education in decolonizing their practice and scholarship through our mission, values, and the Strategic Imperative for Racial Justice and Decolonization.

Agenda

**Program
Background**

**Mentor's
Pathway**

**Mentee's
Pathway**

**Discussion and
Takeaways**

Institution Context

47,000
Total Student Population

26.6%
Of Them Are International Students

55.3%
Of Them Are Graduate Students

96% Retention Rate

92% Graduation Rate

Top Three Int'l Student Countries of Origin

China **India** **S.Korea**

Location: Los Angeles, CA

Research Status: R1

Institution Type: Private

2022 Endowment: \$7.3B

Institution Context

Framework

Personal-Environment-Occupation (PEO) Model (Law et al., 1996 & Arreola et al., 2014)

Kim's (2012) International Student Identity

Engineering Culture

Key Conceptions of Engineering Culture

Engineering is harder than other majors

Engineering is "your whole life"

No time to consider mental health in engineering

An absence of discussions about mental health in engineering

"A meritocracy of difficulty"

"Hardship and suffering"

"Toxically competitive"

Mentorship Program Background and Mission

Context:

- Large private university located in metropolitan area, LA
- Large international student population

Mission:

"By pairing incoming students with their senior peers, the program provides a solid foundation, ensuring every student feels like they belong and is ready to thrive at USC. The program aims to ease the transition into graduate school, promote cross-cultural communication, and build lifelong networks within the welcoming and strongly connected Viterbi community."

Program Objectives

Objectives:

- Elevate new student transition and acclimation
- Empower student development through community-building
- Enhance cross-cultural communication

Activity: Self-Reflection and Sharing

Take a moment to reflect **how your institution currently support international student success** (framework, organizational structure, funding, etc).

Turn to a colleague next to you and share with your partner some background about your institution's support of international students? Which aspects of it have been great? Which aspects of it might use some improvement?

Viterbi Graduate Mentorship Program

~1320 Mentees

~610 Mentors:

"My mentor has been one of my biggest support systems over here."

"Experience sharing is enriching."

Masters Ph.D.

Graduate Student Mentorship Matching

Instructions

- Use the Term Manager to set at least 1 term active. This will enable students to submit requests for that term.
- Once student requests are submitted, Run Matching Algorithm to carry out the matching process.
- View Report Summaries for match data, mentee data, or mentor data.
- Use the Email Manager to configure emails sent out by this system.

Term Manager

Run Matching Algorithm

Create Matches Manually

Match Summary Report

Mentee Summary Report

Mentor Summary Report

Email Manager

Training Session Manager

Mentee Raw Data Report

Mentor Raw Data Report

To All Newly Matched Mentors (20251)

From Address:

Email Subject:

Email Body:

- GROUP SECTION
- Dashboard >
- Members >
- Emails >
- Events >
- Surveys & Forms >
- Member Success** v
- Tracks & Checklists
- Badges
- Service Hours

Tracks & Checklists

Calculate Completions

Search Active

Track 2025 Spring Mentor Roles **4 checklists** Completion

⌵

Track 2025 Spring Mentees' Role **3 checklists** Completion

⌵

Results and Impact

Results and Impact

Results and Impact

Top Mentorship Activities

01

Academic/Course Guidance

- mentors often suggest classes, explain degree requirements, and share study tips or resources.

02

Career/Internship Advice

- Mentors help with resumes, job or internship leads, interview prep, and general career-related guidance.

03

Social/Community Connections

- Mentors introduce mentees to new friends or student groups, encourage participation in campus events, and help them feel more at home.

04

**Regular Check-Ins/
Personal Support**

- Mentors schedule meetings or casually reach out, offering emotional support, practical tips (like housing or life in a new city), and reassurance through challenges.

Takeaways

Technology

- Matching Algorithm
- Database
- Digital course & Quiz
- Customized Communication
- Performance Tracking

Budget

- In-house IT Support
- Share Cost
- Digitalize Certificates
- Volunteers
- Adjust event types
- Bulk Order Swags

Engagement

- A variety of events (types and scales)
- Timely & Constant Communications
- Collaborate with other programs
- Rewards

Questions

- Kristine Arreola, Seonghwa Cho, Celina Phan, Karen Unger, Wen-Pin Chang & Shu-Ping Chen (18 Oct 2024): Exploring mental health experiences and supports among international engineering undergraduate students – insights to inform university support, *European Journal of Engineering Education*, DOI:10.1080/03043797.2024.2417345
- Kim, E. (2012). An alternative theoretical model: Examining psychosocial identity development of international students in the United States. *College Student Journal*, 46(1), 99–113.

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